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**MAIN COMPONENTS OF IMPROVING THE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM
FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF RURAL AREAS**

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The purpose of the conducted research was to analyze theoretical provisions and substantiate practical recommendations for improving the management system of sustainable development in rural areas. The study substantiates that the key components of sustainable rural development encompass four spheres: environmental, social, and economic conditions, as well as the existing institutional environment.

The management system for sustainable rural development should be based on the following principles:

- Systemic approach – integrity, enabling the consideration of the sustainable rural development management system as a whole;
- Consistency – ensuring the presence of all necessary elements of the management system, along with the features of the existing system;
- Hierarchy – structuring the management of all elements in order of subordination from lower to higher levels;
- Multiplicity – allowing for equally accurate descriptions of both individual elements and the rural development management system as a whole;
- Structuring – enabling the tracking of interconnections among system elements and analysis of each management component.

To improve rural development management, it is necessary to build a fundamental management system model that includes all essential elements: goals, objectives, economic actors and entities, influencing factors, operational principles, management methods, system boundaries, and performance indicators.

Key processes in the sphere of economic rural development include:

- Designing and implementing scenarios and forecasts for sustainable economic development, comprehensive programs, and plans;
- Preparing and executing plans and budgets of rural territorial communities;
- Developing and implementing programs to enhance investment attractiveness of businesses and rural areas;
- Creating and executing programs to support agricultural production development.

Rural areas represent a socio-territorial subsystem within the broader system of societal development and possess distinct features. Managing the socio-economic development of rural areas should focus on identifying priority goals for the medium- and long-term.

Sustainable rural development is inseparably linked to increasing agricultural production volumes to ensure the country's food security and independence. Achieving this goal requires the application of innovative approaches in agricultural economics, the use of modern technologies, the promotion of rural employment, along with the monitoring of natural resource consumption and environmental protection.

The formation and implementation of measures to improve the management of sustainable rural development should involve the mobilization of appropriate resources and be accompanied by monitoring their use. Recognizing sustainable rural development as a separate area of state policy will make it possible to establish a scientifically grounded and systematic management mechanism for this domain, ensuring the achievement of the expected results.

Keywords: sustainable development, management, rural areas, strategy, social development, economic development, environmental development.

Introduction. The most pressing issue in the development of rural areas is ensuring their sustainable socio-economic level, which reflects the multidirectional vectors of market, sectoral, infrastructural, socio-cultural, and environmental development. The management of the socio-economic development of rural areas should focus on formulating priority goals for the medium- and long-term, as well as creating optimal conditions for their implementation. The processes taking place in the socio-economic environment require managerial influence from territorial and regional authorities to ensure the most efficient use of production, financial-economic, labor, and natural resources for the purposes of sustainable rural development—improving the standard and quality of life of the rural population.

All this determines the scientific problem, which lies in improving the

mechanism for managing the socio-economic development of rural areas, the implementation of which would ensure improved living standards and quality of life, sustainable agricultural development, and environmentally safe agricultural production.

Review of existing research on the topic. Comprehensive theoretical and methodological studies of the problems of agricultural functioning and rural areas have been carried out by such prominent domestic scholars as Ya. M. Hadzalo [1, 2], A. O. Hutorov [3, 4], V. M. Zhuk [2], O. V. Zakharchuk [5], M. I. Kisil [5], Yu. A. Luzan [1], Yu. O. Lupenko [6], M. Y. Malik [7, 8], M. M. Mohylova [2], N. I. Patyka [9], M. I. Puhachov [9], M. A. Khvesyk [8, 10], and O. H. Shpykuliak [11].

Despite the considerable contribution to the study of issues related to the socio-economic development of rural areas, many theoretical and practical aspects of managing their sustainable development require thorough analysis. This makes the choice of research topic highly relevant and necessitates timely solutions. The purpose of the study is to analyze theoretical provisions and substantiate practical recommendations for improving the management system of sustainable rural development.

Main Part. The main components of sustainable rural development are four spheres, which include the environmental, social, and economic conditions, as well as the existing institutional environment. The management system for sustainable rural development should be based on the following principles:

- Systemic approach – integrity, enabling the consideration of the sustainable rural development management system as a whole.

- Consistency – ensuring the presence of all necessary elements of the sustainable rural development management system, along with the features of the existing system.

- Hierarchy – structuring the management of all elements in order of subordination from lower to higher levels.

- Multiplicity – allowing for equally accurate descriptions of both individual elements and the rural development management system as a whole.

- Structuring – enabling the tracking of interconnections among system elements and analysis of each management component.

In our view, improving rural development management requires building a fundamental management system model, on the one hand, that contains all the necessary elements in the form of goals, objectives, economic entities and actors, influencing factors, operational principles, management methods, system boundaries, and performance indicators of the applied system. On the other hand, all these elements should be integrated into the four priority managed spheres of rural development.

The main goal of economic rural development should be to improve the efficiency of the financial, economic, and production activities of organizations, not only in agribusiness but also in other sectors within a given territory. At the same time, priority tasks should include increasing the tax potential of rural areas in connection with improving the efficiency of budget expenditures, stimulating entrepreneurial activity while simultaneously increasing the volume of attracted investments in rural territorial communities, and boosting the revenues of local budgets.

It should be noted that specific factors in the management system of sustainable rural development for all four managed spheres are the quality of land resources, natural and climatic conditions, production diversification, the availability of recreational resources, as well as the level of infrastructure development and territorial location relative to large administrative centers. The object of management in this area of territorial development is both economic entities and the population directly related to the economic facilities of the territory. The universal management subject for all four managed spheres of rural development is local self-government bodies, which must constantly seek effective links and relations with regional and national authorities, ultimately increasing the efficiency of the management system. Priority management methods in these spheres include legal regulation, the development of effective budgetary policy, and information and communication interaction.

Improving the rural development management system is based on the principles of coordination with the population, consideration of stakeholders' interests, openness, communication, and mutual social responsibility of business, society, and the state.

The key processes in the sphere of economic rural development are:

- Development and implementation of scenarios and forecasts for sustainable economic development, comprehensive programs, and plans.
- Drafting and executing the budgets of rural territorial communities.
- Development and implementation of programs to increase the investment attractiveness of businesses and territories.
- Development and implementation of programs to support agricultural production.

The main restrictive factors slowing the pace of sustainable rural development are:

- Target priorities of the state's economic policy.
- The maximum scope of public services provided in connection with the institutional environment and the level of socio-economic development of the territory.
- The quality of legal and regulatory support for management processes.

Indicators of economic rural development are a set of financial and economic indicators that confirm the ability of rural areas to manage key economic processes, as well as integrated diagnostic indicators of rural development trends.

In the sphere of social rural development, the main goal is to increase human potential. At the same time, the main tasks are to ensure sustainable population growth, reduce unemployment while constantly increasing employment, and improve the human resource potential of rural areas. The object of management in this case is not only the rural population but also social relations and migration.

The key processes in the sphere of social rural development are:

Development and implementation of development scenarios, forecasts, and sustainable demographic growth.

Preparation and implementation of programs to increase the human potential of rural areas.

Development and implementation of territorial programs to support small businesses in creating jobs.

Indicators of social development are integrated demographic indicators and comprehensive indicators for diagnosing trends emerging in the process of managing the social sphere of rural areas.

The main goal of managing the environmental development of rural areas is to preserve a favorable environmental situation in rural territorial entities. At the same time, the priority tasks are to improve the efficiency of environmental monitoring in rural areas and to create motivational incentives for producers to comply with environmental standards. The object of management is the environmental system of rural territorial entities, while the key processes in the field of environmental development include:

- Development of methods for effective monitoring of the environmental condition of rural areas.

- Drafting and adoption by local self-government bodies of legislative acts allowing for the application of administrative and criminal penalties to violators of environmental production standards.

- Introduction of environmental payments into practice.

Indicators of environmental development in rural areas are a set of metrics characterizing the environmental condition of the territory.

The main goal of institutional development in rural areas is to improve the mechanisms of their governance. Within this framework, the tasks to be implemented in rural areas include improving the efficiency of governance systems in local self-government bodies and developing public-private partnerships. In the context of the functioning of the local self-government system, which serves as the object of management, the key processes are improving stakeholder interaction and monitoring the quality of public services. In this case, the indicators are a set of institutional measures that reflect the ability of the economic entity to adjust key processes in rural

areas.

The adopted “Rural Development Concept until 2030” [12] is based on the following provisions:

- Social orientation, with the main goal of improving the standard and quality of life of the population.
- Sustainable development as a necessary system for ensuring positive dynamics in socio-economic processes, their balance, and environmental soundness (in the broad sense of the term).
- Interregional and international cooperation, based on creating conditions for combining regional, interregional, national, and international interests in addressing strategic issues of economic, social, environmental, and territorial development.

The “Rural Development Concept until 2030” is aimed primarily at ensuring sustainable growth in the standard and quality of life of the population and reducing disparities in socio-economic development between territorial entities. Achieving the goals of the Concept is possible only through the consistent formation of a market-oriented and socially oriented economy with clear and stable legislation in the region. Economic development should be based on maximizing the use of the region’s available potential, freeing private initiative while simultaneously strengthening the role of government in ensuring favorable economic conditions. It is necessary to significantly increase production efficiency and accelerate structural reforms.

It should be noted that the Rural Development Concept is based on the classical scenario of building a “tree of goals” with a step-by-step approach to developing, shaping, and implementing strategic guidelines for the region. Like any strategic basis for management decisions, the phased approach to managing the development of rural areas is implemented within a strategic plan.

Its foundation lies in the analysis and monitoring of the conditions for the development of territorial entities, the possible scenarios required to achieve strategic goals, the development of strategically prioritized directions for rural territorial development, and the creation of a mechanism for achieving strategic goals, followed by approval procedures at the regional and national levels.

Most major socio-economic problems are cross-sectoral in nature and essentially share the same root cause—the low level of economic efficiency, insufficient for self-financing and for addressing many urgent issues. Agricultural enterprises face the task of technical and technological re-equipment of production facilities and the introduction of modern equipment and technologies. Ensuring stable competitiveness of products in both domestic and foreign markets is impossible without intensifying innovation processes driven by effective state policy, as well as significantly increasing investment inflows into the production sector.

Thus, the socio-economic development of rural areas is based on the sectoral advantage of agro-industrial production.

To ensure sustainable socio-economic development within a region, it is necessary to identify the main problems in each area of regional development. A region, as a territorial unit with a certain population, requires not only the creation of favorable living conditions but also the establishment of a comfortable environment for the functioning of business organizations operating in various sectors of the regional economy. Against the backdrop of industrial sector development and demographic changes, the state of the natural environment, the potential impact of production and economic activities, and household waste disposal become increasingly relevant, as they collectively affect the ecological situation in rural areas of the region.

In the areas that ensure sustainable rural development—such as the development of non-agricultural sectors, reduction of negative factors affecting the agro-industrial complex, improvement of rural transportation infrastructure, development of small businesses in rural territorial communities, improvement of demographic indicators, raising the living standards of the rural population, addressing healthcare issues, development of rural infrastructure, improvement of education quality, and solving environmental protection challenges—it is essential to identify the key problems in each domain and determine the direction of their development.

The agricultural sector remains the primary branch of the rural economy in

forming the regional product. At the same time, a number of fundamental management challenges must be systematically addressed to ensure its advancement. The main direction of rural development lies in stimulating the rural social sphere, which primarily involves solving demographic issues, improving living standards, and addressing socio-labor problems. Improving living standards requires increasing per capita income in the region, which includes raising the average monthly wage to a level comparable not only with the average annual inflation rate in the country but also with price growth for certain essential goods necessary for the normal life of the rural population. This, in turn, necessitates resolving socio-labor issues related to the structural imbalance between labor demand and supply in rural areas, the low competitiveness of certain population categories in the labor market, and the shortage of highly qualified workers and specialists caused by their outflow to other sectors of the economy.

Thus, rural areas have developed a multidirectional structure of problem zones in the socio-economic sphere. The current state and development prospects of rural areas are influenced by dynamic and rapidly changing processes and factors, many of which are innovative in terms of management and bring adjustments to existing development trends. These changes have ecological, social, and economic dimensions. Their impact manifests in constraints and threats, as well as in prerequisites and opportunities for development, altering processes, mechanisms, and tools for managing territorial development. Managing the socio-economic development of rural areas therefore requires significant improvements to ensure that potential measures align with the realities of development [13].

Conclusions. Rural areas are a socio-territorial subsystem within the framework of social development and have their inherent characteristics. The management of the socio-economic development of rural areas should focus on formulating priority goals for the medium- and long-term perspective.

Sustainable development of rural areas is inextricably linked to increasing agricultural production in order to ensure the country's food security and independence. To achieve this goal, it is necessary to apply an innovative approach in

the agricultural economy, use modern technologies, increase employment in rural areas while simultaneously controlling the consumption of natural resources and protecting the environment.

The development and implementation of measures to improve the management of sustainable rural development should involve the allocation of appropriate resources and be accompanied by monitoring their use. Identifying the issue of sustainable rural development as a separate area of state policy will make it possible to create a scientifically grounded and systematic management mechanism for this domain and ensure the achievement of the expected results.

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